

D2.4

**Actions report for increasing CE technology adsorption
and innovation capacity in the Northern Hungarian region**

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D2.4 – Actions report for increasing CE technology adsorption and innovation capacity in the Northern Hungarian region

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Study for increasing CE technology absorption and innovation capacity in the Northern Hungarian region

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Introduction

The industry of Northern Hungary has a long history, and the area's industrial production remains significant today. However, in terms of GDP and innovation capacity, it lags behind other regions in the country.

This research aims to identify the factors preventing the spread and absorption of circular economy (CE) technologies in Hungarian industrial companies. Understanding these barriers helps develop suggestions that can improve technology absorption and innovation capacity in Northern Hungary. The expected outcome of this research supports the University of Miskolc's third mission, and by deepening the institution's corporate partnerships and introducing new CE-related services, the CiRCLETECH Hub can be established.

CiRCLETECH is a three-year Horizon Europe Twinning project focused on the circular economy, conducted in collaboration with the Dutch Delft University of Technology (TU Delft) and the Finnish Lappeenranta University of Technology (LUT), led by the University of Miskolc. The programme aims to enhance the scientific excellence of the University of Miskolc through cooperation with these institutions and the development of international research partnerships.

The circular approach is increasingly emphasized in European Union directives. Technological innovations in this field contribute to a more sustainable future and currently offer a competitive advantage for companies. As the economy gradually transitions from a linear to a circular model, this competitive advantage will become a basic expectation in the future. Therefore, it is worthwhile for companies to engage in this area. The circular model requires a holistic approach and the cooperation of all economic actors, including government, industry, the population, academia, and municipalities.

Circular technology innovations hold enormous potential, but it is currently under-researched. Although there has already been a report based on a questionnaire survey of the circular practices of Hungarian (mainly large) companies, which highlighted some challenges, research explicitly focusing on industrial companies and seeking to explore the causes in greater depth has not yet been published. Furthermore, the transition presents a more significant challenge for small and medium-sized enterprises (which comprise more than 99% of enterprises in the country), so understanding their perspective is particularly important. This study seeks to fill that gap.

In addition to a questionnaire, we gathered respondents' opinions and experiences through in-depth interviews. SMEs' innovation and absorptive capacity also affect regional development, so addressing their challenges indirectly supports a region's growth.

The first chapter of this study presents the concept of the circular economy, the connecting regulations, and the current state of circular transition in Hungary. Following this, we explore the potential of circular innovations, including the related activities of the University of Miskolc. The next section details the research methodology, followed by the presentation of the results and the answers to the research questions. The study also highlights promising practices discovered during the research and offers recommendations to facilitate the absorption of circular economy technologies in the Northern Hungary region.

1. Framework – Circular economy

1.1. Definition of the circular economy

Many of humankind's problems today relate to climate change and environmental protection. One of the primary directives of EU regulation is to promote sustainability and the transition from a linear economy to a circular economy. The circular economy (CE) is a systems-based model that aims to reduce the use of natural resources and minimize the negative environmental impacts of products throughout their entire life cycle.

Resource reduction can be achieved in two ways: through system-wide optimization of the production-consumption cycle and by recycling the previously used materials and their energy content. Reuse, repair, remanufacture, and refurbishment extend a product's life and maximize the exploitation of the resources. Urban mining involves exploring, extracting, and preparing materials that have entered the cycle once. Urban mining is, therefore, a crucial part of the circular economy, as it reduces the need for primary raw materials.

Figure 1 The model of the circular economy

1.2. EU and Hungarian guidelines and legal background of the circular economy

In recent years, the circular economy concept has been incorporated into European and global policy. Green Deal [1] of the European Union, which aims to achieve carbon neutrality in Europe by 2050, has played a vital role. To achieve a sustainable future, the EU economy must be transformed. The Green Deal contains the most critical steps of this green transition, and the industry serving a clean and circular economy is one of its thematic areas.

1.2.1. Sustainable Product Policy Framework in the EU

Under the objectives of the Green Deal, the European Commission announced the Circular Economy Action Plan [2] in March 2022, which focuses on the creation of sustainable products, and to achieve this, a Sustainable Product Policy Framework has been established, which formulates measures for the following three major areas:

Support for sustainable product design

The expansion of the Ecodesign Directive beyond energy-using products is pending so that the Ecodesign Directive can be applied to the broadest possible range of products and achieve circularity.

Empowering consumers and public purchasers

The Commission will propose minimum mandatory criteria and targets for Green Public Procurement (GPP) in the sectoral legislation and will gradually introduce mandatory reporting to monitor the spread of green public procurement without imposing an unreasonable administrative burden on public purchasers.

Promoting circularity in production processes

Establishing a support system for industrial symbiosis - using digital technologies and applying the EU's environmental technology verification scheme as an EU certification mark.

1.2.2. Key product value chains

Electronics and ICT

The "*Circular Initiative for Electronics*" for existing and new electronic devices could promote a longer product lifespan (e.g., mandatory repair option and reuse).

Batteries and vehicles

It aims to take measures to improve collection and recycling rates for all batteries (especially from electric vehicles), ensure the recovery of valuable materials, and review end-of-life vehicle requirements.

Packaging

The EU wants to tighten the basic requirements for packaging allowed on its market (e.g., reducing packaging waste, designing packaging for reuse, and reducing packaging complexity).

Plastics

The EU will propose mandatory requirements for the recycled content of plastics and measures to reduce plastic waste in packaging, construction materials, and vehicles.

Textile industry

Regarding the use of primary raw materials and water, the textile industry has the fourth largest impact after food, housing, and transport. This is why the EU intends to establish a flagship sustainability strategy for textiles (e.g., sustainable textiles, increased separate collection, reuse of used textiles).

Construction and buildings

The construction industry requires vast resources, accounting for around 50% of all extracted materials. By increasing the efficiency of material use, 80% of this raw material demand could be saved. It is proposed that recycling as secondary raw material should be considered at the design stage, mandatory life-cycle assessment should be applied to public procurement of construction works, and higher recovery rates for construction waste should be introduced.

Food, water, and nutrients

The food value chain is responsible for a significant resource and environmental burden, with an estimated 20% of all food produced in the EU wasted or wasted (33% in Hungary). This is why the EU aims to reduce food waste.

In addition to these objectives, the Circular Economy Action Plan also sets out efforts to change the overall socio-economic model in horizontal areas (education, research and development, and business models). Implementing the proposed policy measures may contribute to reducing material use and related environmental externalities, help the EU exploit its competitive advantages, accelerate green innovation and investment, and reduce the product and material dependence of the economy.

1.2.3. Hungarian targets for the circular economy

A study entitled "Towards a national strategy for a circular economy in Hungary" [3] was prepared with the support of the OECD and the EU to develop a circular economy model in Hungary. One of the study's key findings is that **if Hungary does not take appropriate steps to establish a circular economy, its future material use is projected to increase by one-third by 2050 compared to 2017 levels.**

Suppose material consumption increases at this rate by 2050. In that case, there is a risk that Hungary will not be able to meet the targets set out in the Green Deal, as increased material use would create a significant environmental burden, including an increase in greenhouse gas emissions.

The study identifies key areas and high-impact measures critical for the transition to a circular economy in Hungary. These include biomass and food, construction, and plastics.

Biomass and food industry

Bio-waste is defined as biodegradable waste from gardens or parks, food, and kitchen waste generated in households, offices, restaurants, wholesalers, catering, restaurants, and retail establishments, and similar waste generated in food processing plants. At least half of biowaste is food waste, which must be collected separately from 2024 per EU regulations.

The fulfilment of this requirement is a serious challenge for several countries, including Hungary, as they currently do not solve the comprehensive management of bio-waste with a thorough, introduced solution. In general, it can be said that most of the food waste is produced in households. Hungary performs relatively well in this regard, creating an amount below the EU average per year (62 kg/person/year). Based on the latest research of the NÉBIH [4], 594,000 tons of food waste is generated in households in Hungary every year. This means a serious economic loss for the population, as 20% of the food they buy is thrown away, an annual loss of HUF 380 billion.

In Hungary, MOHU has only started a separate collection of kitchen biowaste on a pilot basis, and long-term experience is not yet available. The collection of bio-waste has the potential to save materials (production of high-quality compost) and energy (in the form of biogas recovery), which can be the basis for creating a circular bioeconomy with the appropriate management of agricultural by-products and waste. Given its potential, Hungary can become a leader in the region by applying appropriate business models.

Construction

The construction industry has significant potential for the transition to a circular economy. Currently, more than 50% of the raw materials used in our country are used in the built environment. In addition, the industry is responsible for about one-third of Hungary's waste generation. Therefore, to develop a circular economy in the construction sector, the following tasks should be supported:

- strengthening and promoting the certification of secondary (secondary source) building materials,
- developing secondary building materials, supporting innovation,
- make the selective collection of construction materials mandatory on construction and renovation sites,
- promoting the reuse and renovation of existing buildings as opposed to new construction.

Plastics

Plastics have recently come in for a lot of criticism from an environmental point of view (mainly because of the pollution caused by microplastics), with some people calling for a ban. However, without engineering plastics, our everyday life would be unimaginable. They have become an indispensable raw materials in vehicles, electronic devices, furniture, construction, and textiles. In Hungary, the plastics industry is also strategic, from raw material production to finished product manufacture, with significant circular potential. They serve as critical inputs in several sectors of the national economy, most notably packaging and construction. Plastics currently account for a quarter of all packaging materials used in the country. However, up to one-third of plastic waste is recycled. Hungary is currently facing a challenge in meeting the relevant EU targets. Moving away from primary plastics towards recycled plastics could also be a solution for a circular economy in this area.

1.2.4. Description of current Hungarian (legislation) practice

Introduction of a new Hungarian waste management system

According to the current EU Directive (and the corresponding Hungarian Waste Management Act), starting in 2035, a maximum of 10 % of the weight of municipal waste generated per year may be landfilled.

Therefore, to meet the directives, more separate collection systems must be introduced in EU Member States, including Hungary, as about 50% of municipal solid waste is currently

landfilled. By 2035, the recycling rate of municipal solid waste should be increased to 65%, which is currently only 35% in Hungary [5].

This is one of the reasons why the Hungarian government has decided to introduce an entirely new approach to waste management in Hungary from 1 July 2023. Under the concession, MOL Hulladékgazdálkodási Zrt. (MOHU) will be responsible for operating the solid municipal waste management system in Hungary for 35 years and will thus also be accountable for meeting the EU targets.

Extended producer responsibility (EPR)

In addition to restructuring the waste management system, the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) scheme will be introduced in 2023, replacing the previous environmental product fee scheme. EPR was required by an EU Directive to be introduced by all Member States, as previously, different Member States had applied different principles for producer responsibility for each waste stream. The MOHU also collects the revenue from the EPR fees. Still, in return, the MOHU is responsible for meeting the EU's collection and recovery targets for each waste stream.

Introduction of DRS (Deposit-Return System)

Hungary has also introduced the Deposit-Return System (called REpontos) for single-use drinks packaging from 2024, based on the EU's single-use drinks packaging directive. The system, which applies to packaging with a capacity of between 0.1 and 3 liters, will also cover aluminum cans and bottles and plastic packaging. MOHU in Hungary will also coordinate the system under the concession agreement. MOHU has committed to reach the EU target of 90% take-back by 2029. The system started on 1 July 2024, when only beverage containers with the new IDs will be available in shops. With the introduction of the system, experts expect a reduction in illegal littering and a higher recovery target for plastics and aluminium cans, based on European practices. The system will also impose a new obligation on producers and distributors to register their beverage products in the Deposit Refund System (DRS) for products placed on the Hungarian market.

1.3. The emergence of the circular economy in national innovation policy

In the 2014-2020 period of the EU, a joint policy instrument, the Smart Specialization Strategy [6] (hereinafter: S3), focuses on developing unique, area-based, and specialization directions. In the 2021-2027 development cycle, the S3 aims to contribute to the policy

objective of the Cohesion Policy, "Smarter Europe by supporting innovation and economic transformation and modernization."

In the S3 strategy adopted by the Hungarian government in 2021, the circular economy has a prominent place within the critical area of "Resource-efficient economy," where the circular economy aims to:

- Waste minimisation, resource use reduction, and environmental impact were identified primarily through transforming the life cycle of products.
- It encompasses corporate activities such as sustainable design, whereby companies consider the entire life cycle of a product from the design stage through the selection of its materials and function and strive to reduce its environmental footprint.

Research, development, and innovation (RDI) activities related to the circular economy need to be addressed:

- more sustainable packaging and storage,
- more efficient treatment and reuse of secondary raw materials,
- exploring new applications and production possibilities for new materials with a lower environmental impact, which are currently not competitive due to production costs,
- adopting solutions to minimise waste, where foreign good practice is more effective and resource-efficient than Hungarian solutions,
- in the field of maintenance, technical service, repair, renovation, and remanufacturing.

The S3 RDI target for the circular economy:

- Strengthening RDI to mitigate the effects of climate change and stimulating innovation in this direction across the innovation ecosystem.
- To strengthen RDI activities aimed at implementing a circular economy, waste minimisation, and reduction of environmental pressures, to promote the diffusion of innovations in this direction, and to adopt good practices.
- Supporting the development of a bio-based economy.
- Innovative solutions and skills development to raise awareness of the resource-efficient economy and to spread a conscious approach.

The circular economy is also an essential objective of the Hungarian Competitiveness Strategy 2024, which covers 2024-2030 [7]. This strategy includes six priority industries: automotive, health, food, raw materials, information and communication technology, and creative industries.

In the vision of the Hungarian raw material industry (chemicals, metals, plastics, glass, rubber) plays a prominent role in the circular economy:

- Our country's circular economy has to recycle almost all waste into materials.
- Hungary will produce 50% of the steel the automotive, defence, and construction industries need.
- Hungarian companies recycle raw materials.

Table 1 Strategic objectives of the Hungarian raw materials sectors - related priority proposals

Strategic objective	Priority proposals
Implementing the green transition (circular economy)	1. Public support for green transition projects 2. Promote the use of recycled materials
Increasing the competitiveness of Hungarian companies	3. Making applications more flexible (one-stop-shop)
Supplier development	5. Supporting Hungarian suppliers in establishing contacts with international companies coming to Hungary
Research and development	6. Assessing Hungarian raw material assets to secure critical raw materials 7. Support for cooperative materials technology development: for R&D activities based on cross-sectoral collaboration

The OECD 2023 study [3] set out the targets for Hungary to reach by 2040:

- To limit material use, the government is investing in research and introducing incentives to promote resource efficiency through innovation, eco-design, and product sharing and reuse.
- To close the material recycling and use materials more sustainably, measures will be taken to double Hungary's recycled material rate (from 6.8% to 15%).
- Hungary aims to increase the number of circular economy jobs by 30% (to 2.5% of the total workforce) in industry, agriculture, and services.

1.4. Circular economy in Hungarian companies

Currently, there are no accurate numbers on how many companies already operate entirely according to the circular approach in Hungary. However, several professional associations have been founded in connection with the circular economy, the two largest of which are:

Circular Economy Platform

The Circular Economy Platform in Hungary was launched in 2018 by the Business Council for Sustainable Development of Hungary (BCSDH), the Embassy of the Netherlands, and the Ministry of Innovation and Technology. So far, 99 companies and organisations have joined the Platform. This does not mean that all these companies are already operating in a circular way, but they intend to do so in the future.

Circular Economy Technology Platform

It is coordinated by the MOL-PE Circular Economy Science Park Zrt., which mainly examines the potential for developing the circular economy from an engineering and technological point of view through several committees. In 2024, several conferences were organised with the cooperation of the Ministry of Energy.

The circular economy also plays a prominent role in the activities of the Hungarian government within the Ministry of Energy, headed by the State Secretary for the Environment and the Circular Economy.

The Circular Economy Platform surveyed the current state of the circular economy in 2019 and 2023 using an online questionnaire [8]. The survey aimed to identify the main challenges of the transition to circularity and to identify solutions already in place in the field. Most respondents were large companies, with many service providers represented in the sample. Survey respondents are currently mainstreaming circularity in their operational processes, consumer awareness programmes, and waste and energy reduction, and plan to mainstream it in their supplier requirements in the future.

Although last year's survey shows that firms have made progress on circularity compared to 2019, there was no change in the majority's view that moving to circularity will mean an expense. A large majority of respondents believe that government incentive programmes, mainly financial, are the primary support for the transition. Still, regulations, central development strategies, and learning about good practices in companies can also greatly help. Respondents consider that the most significant challenges are in the areas of secondary materials (recovery and market development) and consumer awareness, while the most important potential for improvement is seen in production processes and waste.

2. The potential of circular technology and innovations

2.1. Technology absorption

Technology absorption is when a company acquires, adapts, and utilizes new technology from an external source. This transaction occurs between the transferring and the receiving organizations. Absorptive capacity refers to acquiring technological knowledge, integrating new solutions into existing systems, adopting new tools and methods, and adapting them to the firm's needs if necessary. The external source (the transferring party) is often a higher education institution. [9]

Innovation capacity reflects how effectively a company can introduce and develop new solutions, processes, products, and technologies and further improve existing ones. It is critical to competitiveness and adaptation to economic changes. [10]

Innovation capacity and technology absorption influence each other mutually. Technology absorption enhances a company's innovation capacity by laying the foundation for launching its developments. An organization's absorption effectiveness depends on its resources and innovation capacity. The growth potential inherent in innovation capacity is significant for SMEs [11].

The technology absorption and innovation capacity of companies within a region indirectly affect the region's economic development, meaning economic growth can be achieved by improving these capacities. Figure 2 illustrates the process of technology absorption from the perspective of the demand side of technology, the companies. Companies must adopt new technologies to generate demand to fulfill their economic goals and adapt to the market changes. Introducing new technologies relies on scientific research results conducted by higher education institutions, which are utilized through technology development, consultation, services, and transfer. Enterprises optimize the technology according to their specific characteristics during the technology innovation stage. The next step is integrating the technology into the company's existing processes to become a fundamental element of production and operations. Ultimately, this leads to industrial development, and modern industry fosters economic growth in the region. [12]

The materialization of knowledge promotes regional economic growth in a self-reinforcing manner. The more developed an area's industry, the more attractive it becomes to investors and firms, who provide the demand and capital for new research. This, in turn, increases the region's technology absorption and innovation capacity. An advanced industry creates jobs and strengthens universities (e.g., through research projects, collaborations with companies,

and the development of educational programs to meet corporate needs), ultimately improving the well-being and socioeconomic status of the people living in the area.

Figure 2 The impact of technology absorption on regional growth (based on [12])

2.2. RDI corporate relations of the University of Miskolc

2.2.1. RDI management at the University of Miskolc

In 2017, the FIEK (Centre for Industrial Cooperation in Higher Education) was established at the University of Miskolc with the mission to promote the institution's research and development (R&D) activities and strengthen it on a business basis. To this end, it maintains an ongoing dialogue with the university's research organisations to select and present technologies and research results that are relevant to the market. Main activities:

- Coordinates and harmonises research and innovation activities at the University of Miskolc.
- Promoting and disseminating the research and development results of the University of Miskolc, helping to exploit them.
- Developing research, development, and innovation (RDI) partnerships with external partners.
- Manages institutional intellectual property (IP), facilitating intellectual property sale and commercial exploitation.
- Creating a university knowledge map (competence maps) to make RDI services.

- Organising innovation and research management training and supporting students in innovation and start-ups.

FIEK aims to contribute to the success of RDI through forward-looking and effective collaborations.

According to the University of Miskolc's regulations, the organisational tasks of RDI activities (from tendering to invoicing) are coordinated by the newly established RDI Management Department of the FIEK, which also organises requests for proposals for academic units independently. The implementation of the one-stop shop RDI system has achieved a number of results since 2023:

- standardised offer and order templates (new sharepoint system introduced),
- reducing paper-based administration,
- Reduced lead time for RDI administrative processes,
- an increase in the number of projects involving more than one faculty,
- a searchable web-based portfolio of RDI services (competencies and measurements) for industry.

2.2.2. The University of Miskolc's corporate network

The University of Miskolc maintains contacts with companies inside and outside the region, with regular RDI contracts with around 150-200 companies. The primary industries commissioned by the institution are the traditional engineering fields of chemical/energy and mechanical/automotive, but the construction, energy, and waste management industries are also increasingly robust. These industries are also of particular importance because the major players in the region (including the MOL group, the Bosch group, the MVM group, and BorsodChem) are the main partners of the higher education institution.

The University of Miskolc is the knowledge center of the Northern Hungary region, but this does not mean that business contacts only come from this region. Its RDI mandates are based on traditional working relationships that go back several decades, and the university's focus areas have also been designed with corporate innovation needs in mind.

2.2.3. Competences related to the circular economy

At the University of Miskolc, the directions in the technical fields have been developed over the past decades, which can be found in the University's Institutional Development Plan 2021. This was facilitated by creating the Centres of Excellence Program in 2011. The University has unique activities in several teaching and research areas not found in other universities in Hungary (e.g., foundry, materials science, oil mining). The focus areas are:

- Sustainable natural resource management
- Advanced materials and technologies
- Innovative engineering
- Logistics and digital technologies

Detailed descriptions of each competence are available on the website <https://www.unimiskolc.hu/kutatas-fejlesztes-innovacio/fokuszteruletek/>. Within each focus area, several competencies have been identified, and the 74 competence sheets are available in a single format, as an online package, in Hungarian and English.

Although it can be seen that the names of the focus areas do not include the term circular economy (the competence areas were defined in 2021), there are still multiple links to the circular economy in the majority of the competences. The most common points are in the areas of *Sustainable Natural Resource Management* and *Advanced Materials and Technologies*, the most important of which are highlighted here.

Key competencies related to the circular economy:

- Innovative environmental monitoring and assessment: environmental modelling tasks (in environmental assessment, impact assessment, and environmental informatics).
- Sustainable water management: the exploration, sustainable, and safe use of natural water in its many forms and conditions, as well as wastewater treatment and sewage sludge recovery.
- Geothermal energy exploration: complex research of the problems associated with the exploration and exploitation of medium and deep geothermal systems.
- Energy and storage utilisation of geological resources: the complex and synergistic use of geological resources for energy and storage in an environmentally conscious and environmentally focused manner.
- Processing of secondary raw materials and waste: mechanical, chemical, physico-chemical, biological, and thermal processing operations for recycling in material.
- Exploration for critical mineral resources: primary ore and industrial minerals.
- Metal extraction, production, and purification: pyro- and hydrometallurgical processes for the processing and disposal of solid and liquid metal wastes.
- Ceramic and silicate materials and technologies: investigating the potential of secondary raw materials for the ceramics industry.
- Polymer technologies: developing new products from secondary raw materials.
- Carbon-neutral industrial energy: pyrolysis-based energy developments.

- Environmentally friendly machine and product design: design supported by life cycle analysis,
- Design of waste logistics systems: optimisation of collection and transport systems for used products and waste.

2.3. Circular technology innovations

In the future, companies are likely to engage in technology absorption and innovation related to the following CE areas:

- Reuse and recycle batteries and solar panels (hydrometallurgy) and recover critical raw materials from them as secondary raw materials.
- Further development of predictive maintenance (artificial intelligence) and industrial digitalisation techniques for energy-efficient industrial production.
- Research and development of technologies for converting municipal solid waste and construction demolition waste into secondary raw materials (cement replacement, CO₂ capture, etc.).
- Automation of waste sorting technologies with the support of artificial intelligence.
- Development of hydrogen technology replacement of existing primary energy sources.
- Product development based on secondary raw materials from the construction industry.
- Development of complex circular business and technological models.

Most of these topics are already being addressed in knowledge centres, including the University of Miskolc. Innovation opportunities are available to companies through both national and international innovation service providers. In most cases, the diffusion of technological developments to industry has not yet occurred, so the priority is to build pilot solutions in specific industries.

There are international and national funding frameworks to support research projects and investments, particularly for SMEs. While large companies are generally able to implement these developments on their own, an increasing number are also using governmental support for their innovations.

3. Research Methodology

The research task was performed using primary research methods. First, we used a questionnaire to investigate the attitudes of Hungarian industrial companies toward circular technologies. Subsequently, qualitative in-depth interviews were conducted with a subset of the respondents to gain a more detailed insight into the answers to the questions in the questionnaire and the participants' opinions. We chose individual interviews, as we assumed that the participants would feel freer to express their views in this format compared to group discussions.

3.1. Research questions

Based on the purpose and the expected outcome of the research, four research questions were formulated:

Q1: What knowledge do companies have about the circular economy?

Q2: What does the absorption of CE technologies mean for companies, and how do they apply circularity in their operation?

Q3: What are the barriers to the absorption of CE technologies?

Q4: What role can the University of Miskolc play in eliminating the barriers to the absorption of CE technologies?

The survey focused on examining the attitudes and challenges of the Hungarian industrial SME sector towards circular technology. SMEs determine their operational strategies, including sustainability-related decisions, whereas large, primarily multinational companies typically follow central directives from the foreign parent companies. Larger companies can also allocate more resources to the transition to circularity, making the process easier. However, analysing large companies is also essential, as these advantages mentioned above enable them to offer well-established good practices.

3.2. Questionnaire

The questionnaire, which was tailored to the research questions, consisted of five parts and a total of seventeen questions (see Appendix 1). Several test questionnaires were completed before the final version was sent out, and the set of questions was refined based on feedback from these tests.

The survey was conducted online using a form created in Microsoft Forms. All enterprises listed in the R&D database managed by FIEK received the questionnaire via a newsletter, and a LinkedIn post with the same content was also created and shared on FIEK's profile. Approximately one thousand businesses were invited to participate in the research.

The first block of the questionnaire aimed to gather information about the company's profile (size, region, industrial subclassification according to the Hungarian Central Statistical Office). The next part sought answers related to the companies' image of the circular economy, while the third section focused on the absorption of circular technologies. The penultimate section aimed to assess the demand for services related to the circular economy in connection with the Q4 research question, while the final section allowed respondents to indicate their willingness to participate in an interview.

3.3. In-depth interviews with companies

To gain a deeper understanding of CE technology absorption by companies, we conducted approx. 30-minute individual in-depth interviews with representatives of some firms. These interviews were conducted online via Microsoft Teams. While the interviews were structured around a pre-written set of questions (see Appendix 2), additional questions were asked improvisationally in response to the participants' answers, following the natural flow of the conversation, adapting to the emerging topics, and allowing space for the participants to share their views.

In each case, the interviews began with an introduction to the company's activities and its current and planned circular practices. This was followed by a discussion of the obstacles to circular technology absorption and, if relevant for the given enterprise, the opportunities and challenges related to secondary raw materials. The final part of the conversation focused on the role the subjects expect higher education institutions to play in the transition to circular operation and explored the potential connections between the company and the University of Miskolc in relation to circular technologies.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Results of the questionnaire

The questionnaire was completed by 36 companies, and the results were evaluated using Microsoft Excel.

4.1.1. Company profile

Figure 3 Territorial distribution of the companies participating in the research (more than one site is possible)

Responses were received from almost all industries. Most companies manufacture raw metal materials and metal processing products, followed by the production of computers, electronics, optical products, and vehicle products. Besides industrial production companies, several service providers and waste management and processing companies also participated, ensuring that all circular economy actors were represented in the survey. 64% of the companies were SMEs, and 36% were large enterprises. Respondents came from all seven regions of Hungary, with the majority (19 companies) operating in Northern Hungary.

4.1.2. Knowledge of the circular economy

It is positive that almost all respondents – except for one – had heard of the circular economy. Most (30) were familiar with the concept, while five had heard of it but were not very knowledgeable about this field. The correct definition of the circular economy (where we emphasized that it is a system-based model that focuses on the most efficient use of

resources) was identified by the majority, with only three respondents mistakenly believing that the model focuses solely on efficient waste recycling.

Figure 4 Knowledge of guidelines and frameworks related to the circular economy

It is also encouraging that more than half of the firms have heard of all the circular economy-related guidelines and frameworks listed in the questionnaire. About 30% were familiar with the content of each document, and only a small proportion had not heard of them and did not know their content. Most companies are familiar with the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) system, while the National Waste Management Plan is the least familiar. The percentage values in Figure 4 are rounded to whole numbers.

4.1.3. Circular operation and technology

Figure 5 Does your company consider the aspects of the circular economy during its activities?

36% of the companies fully incorporate circular economy principles into their activities, while almost half (47%) partially do so. 14% do not currently apply these principles but plan to do so in the future. Only one enterprise stated that they do not currently consider circularity and have no plans to adopt it.

Figure 6 Areas of application of the circular approach in the analysed companies (currently and in the future)

Figure 6 shows how many companies use the circular approach in the listed areas. The questionnaire revealed that most enterprises currently apply the aspects of the circular economy to managing production waste, energy consumption, and manufacturing technology. Slightly behind these were raw material procurement and business models. The circular approach appears the least in terms of requirements towards their suppliers, consumer attitudes shaping programmes, and product life cycle monitoring. Only two companies reported not applying circularity in any area. Two additional areas, "in-house training" and "application of law," were received as other answer options.

In the future, the surveyed companies plan to apply circular principles in more areas. Half of the respondents indicated plans to improve circularity in logistic activities, but energy consumption and production waste management were also popular responses. Slightly behind these, many enterprises also marked the areas of raw material procurement and business model. Only a tiny part of the respondents wants circularity-related developments in the area of consumer attitudes shaping programmes and monitoring the product life cycle, and only a quarter of the firms plan to take steps towards circular product design. Only three companies do not want to develop in any of the areas covered by the questionnaire. One respondent mentioned "exploitation of regulations" as another answer to this question.

Figure 7 Factors affecting the adoption of circular technological solutions

1 – No effect at all, 2 – Rather no effect, 3 – Moderate effect, 4 – Rather has an impact, 5 – Substantial effect

The next question aimed to assess whether external or internal pressure drives the adoption of circular technologies and to measure the influence of different factors. Respondents felt that the advantages gained in tender/grant evaluations and the potential for improving the company’s image have the greatest impact, followed by the ownership/management demand for greener operation. More than half of the company representatives believe that regulatory/legal pressure has very large effect. A change in employee attitudes/demands was seen as the least influential factor. The percentage values in Figure 7 are rounded to whole numbers.

Figure 8 Factors preventing the adoption of circular technological solutions

1 – Does not prevent at all, 2 – Rather does not prevent, 3 – Moderately prevents, 4 – Rather prevents, 5 – Strongly prevents

Based on our preliminary assumptions, we identified factors that may hinder the adoption of circular technologies. The next question examined the extent of these barriers. The results show that bureaucratic regulation and the prioritization of other economic factors are the biggest obstacles to absorbing CE technology. Most companies believed they had adequate relational capital, information, and expertise to transition to circular operations, making these factors the least likely to impede the change. One respondent mentioned that "we manufacture products optimized for one-time use based on customer demand," while another cited "lack of legal inconsistency" as a barrier, which relates to the complexity of the legislation. The percentage values in Figure 8 are rounded to whole numbers.

The final question in this section asked about the company's involvement in circular economy-related professional activities, which can indicate the demand for programmes in this field.

Figure 9 Membership in a professional community, participation in conferences and events related to the circular economy

More than half of the company representatives had attended a circular economy-related conference or event recently, 36% had not yet attended but planned to, and only three respondents stated they had neither attended nor planned to attend. Almost half of the respondents are members of a circularity-related professional community, nearly 40% are not yet members but would like to join in the future, and five respondents are not members and do not intend to join.

4.1.4. Assessment of demand for CE services

Figure 10 In which areas would your company require external services (consulting) for the development of the circular operation model?

The final section of the questionnaire aimed to assess the demand for services related to the circular economy. This helps to understand the role higher education institutions can play in fostering the transition of companies to circular operations. One of the research goals is to develop new services based on business needs, laying the foundation for creating the CIRCLETECH Hub.

Almost half of the enterprises would require external services in the areas of innovation services and waste management consulting to develop a circular operating model. In addition, many respondents indicated a demand for tender, grant, funding opportunities consultation, and technology consultation services, while business consulting was the least in demand. In addition to the areas listed, the following appeared among other responses: attitude-shaping advice related to the circular economy, customer acquisition, training and education, and help in following and interpreting legislation. Nearly three-quarters (72%) of the enterprises participating in the research would use university-offered services in the field of CE technology.

4.2. Results of the in-depth interviews

During the interviews, we encouraged participants to share their opinions, and we anticipated that confidential information might be revealed. To preserve anonymity, we do not publish the company profiles of the subjects (even with name changes) containing company-specific data. The good practices of some selected enterprises are discussed in detail in another chapter, along with their names. In this section, the results are presented in a way that prevents the identification of the responding companies. The responses given during the interviews were grouped according to the questions and aggregated.

4.2.1. General information on the interviewees

Nine companies, representing a quarter of the respondents to the questionnaire, participated in the interviews. Five of the participants represented SMEs, while four represented large companies. The interviewees were CEOs or plant managers and in the case of one large company, the person responsible for the area most closely related to circularity. Most of the examined companies operate in Northern Hungary, while the rest are in Central Hungary, Western, Central, or Southern Transdanubia. The entire circular cycle was covered in activity, with companies involved in manufacturing, energy production, repair, and waste processing.

The interviews were conducted with companies that already, at least partially, incorporate aspects of the circular economy into their activities, and more than half of them fully operate according to these principles. All those interviewed had heard of the circular economy and were familiar with its definition. Almost all of them have attended an event and/or are members of a professional community related to the topic or at least plan to become involved.

4.2.2. Circular practices and planned developments in companies

The good practices revealed in some companies are detailed in *Chapter 5.1*. This section describes the circular practices of all the companies interviewed, focusing on common features.

The solutions related to circularity currently applied by the surveyed enterprises are summarized by area:

- Materials:
 - minimizing the use of raw materials
 - through appropriate product design (e.g., reduced complexity, simplified design)
 - optimization through material development (e.g., alloys that ensure required mechanical properties while reducing material consumption)
 - procuring materials from local suppliers
 - using recycled materials
 - using recyclable materials
 - using environmentally friendly paints
 - minimizing packaging materials
 - using recycled and/or recyclable packaging materials
 - preparing industrial secondary raw materials for further processing
 - setting regulations related to circularity for their suppliers
- Waste:
 - minimizing generated waste
 - recycling production waste back into production
 - handling manufacturing waste (off-site recycling at a partner)
 - collecting, pre-treating, and selling waste
 - adequate waste disposal
 - recycling waste
 - extracting precious metals
 - utilizing by-products in other industries

- Manufacturing:
 - producing a new generation of products with minimal modification to the old production line (adding new stations)
 - measuring environmental impacts during production
 - determining performance indicators related to sustainability
 - recovering carbon dioxide produced during manufacturing and using it in other processes
- Logistics:
 - local distribution and sales
 - processing local waste
- Repair and maintenance:
 - repairing defective or scrap products
 - repairing and refurbishing used products
 - remanufacturing products with additional functionality
 - applying product lifetime-extending methods
 - service activities and maintenance
- Energy:
 - reducing and optimizing energy consumption in existing plants
 - constructing plants that ensure efficient energy use
 - utilizing waste heat from pneumatic systems (e.g., for additional heating, water heating, or office floor heating)
 - optimizing energy use through continuous measurement and control
 - using and monitoring energy efficiency indicators
 - meeting energy demand with on-site biogas plants
 - insulating the production system adequately
 - installing solar panels
- Reduction of environmental pollution:
 - minimizing wastewater
 - reducing CO₂ emissions by lowering energy consumption
 - setting Net Zero strategic goals
 - implementing dust-free concrete and green areas to reduce air pollution
 - collecting and pre-treating rainwater
 - creating bee pastures
 - using electric cars and installing electric car chargers
 - environmental awareness programmes for the employees

It is evident that most examples relate to materials and waste; companies mainly focus on these areas when considering circular technologies. They also pay attention to reducing environmental pollution and improving the efficiency of their energy systems. Circular solutions are applied least in logistics and activities, which extends product lifetime. Circular product design was mentioned in only one case, and even then, it only concerned materials.

Several company managers noted that greener operations help comply with regulations, tenders, and EU directives and offer important marketing advantages. For example, one company, as a supplier, tries to provide products that can be produced in the most environmentally friendly way possible. A conscious consumer base has emerged, and many of this company's partners aim to produce finished products that meet these new needs.

One interviewee, representing a company in electricity production, shared that they encourage users to conserve energy through various consumer awareness programmes. Other companies, however, do not conduct similar awareness-raising activities.

A common trait among the multinational enterprises involved in the research is that their parent companies are dedicated to sustainability, even if environmentally conscious solutions do not always have immediate financial benefits. This commitment stems from the perspective of foreign management and ownership and customer expectations because many of their customers seek environmentally conscious suppliers. These companies' sustainability strategies include the area of circular economy, which focuses on the efficient use of materials. Foreign headquarters set the strategy and related performance goals at the factory level. As large organizations, they have the financial resources to invest in circular technologies, and they expect their partners to comply with specific regulations and standards. Their parent companies are significant enough industry players to participate in professional consultations before legislative changes are introduced, allowing them to advocate for their interests.

In the future, several companies are planning developments and investments related to circularity. For example, one manufacturing company is acquiring a modern production line that will significantly reduce the plant's energy consumption. Another company's newest plant was built with energy efficiency in mind, aiming to minimize energy losses.

Most respondents see the key to achieving a circular operating model as related to material use (reducing consumption and using recycled materials) and developing material-associated technologies. Recycling materials contributes to a more sustainable future and is also more inexpensive in some cases. Several participants mentioned aluminum as an

example. Extracting aluminum from waste requires less energy than producing it from its primary raw material, alumina.

Companies in the automotive industry participating in the research use the International Material Data System (IMDS) database. This database provides information about materials used in the automotive industry, including the composition of parts, the proportion of harmful substances in products, and compliance with EU standards. It also facilitates reporting to customers.

4.2.3. Barriers to the absorption and spread of circular technologies

Participants could explain the negative attitudes characterizing their company and industry regarding the transition to circular operation in this part. They voiced their fears, potential risks, weaknesses (internal factors preventing the achievement of the goal), and dangers (external factors preventing the accomplishment of the goal). Several people also expressed their thoughts about today's most significant obstacles to realizing the circular economy, regardless of industry.

One participant pointed out that although the European Union directives increasingly demand the consideration of refurbishment and remanufacturing in product design, this is not realized in practice. According to him, newer electronic devices are much more difficult to disassemble without damage than older devices, and manufacturers do not prioritize repairability and maintainability. He thinks stricter central regulations are the only solution to this problem. He believes there is great potential in extending the life cycle of electronic equipment (which he believes could even be doubled), but this requires new, sustainable, profitable business models. Introducing repaired devices into the market will require manufacturers and existing service providers to develop new services and activities. He suggested a well-established method for network devices as an example: ownership remains with the manufacturer, who provides the device as a service. This way, the manufacturer's goal is to extend the product's life as much as possible, and regular software updates for network system components are an important part of this model.

In for-profit companies, economic considerations always take priority. Several participants explained that sustainability and social responsibility primarily serve PR purposes. Some noted that sustainability efforts in regulations impose additional administrative and documentation burdens on them (e.g., the obligation to prepare an ESG report), representing significant costs for SMEs. Many company managers feel lost due to rapidly changing regulations, which are complex to follow and challenging when trying to find a workforce with the expertise to perform the related tasks.

Smaller businesses see the economic policy as Hungary's biggest obstacle to progress. One company's manager noted, for example, that they were at a disadvantage compared to their foreign competitors due to high energy prices. While the government adjusted gas prices to an acceptable level during the energy price surge, no such adjustment was made for other costs (e.g., system usage fees), making energy very expensive. They are forced to incorporate these extra costs into their product prices, but their market is unwilling to pay for it, opting for competitors in countries with lower energy prices.

Several participants reported significant losses due to the weakening of the Hungarian forint during currency exchanges. Additionally, many laws and regulations are amended overnight without consultation with industry players, which creates unpredictability and discourages investment. This is especially critical in industries characterized by long return periods.

Regarding R&D-related investments, companies only apply for projects they would implement without financial support. One respondent explained that even in joint projects with universities (carried out in consortia), all the responsibility falls on them. Tasks are not clearly defined, processes are mired in bureaucracy, and payments often come in the form of post-financing (or delayed), so they prefer not to engage in such collaborations. Companies prefer to join projects that are already well-prepared with well-defined activities, reducing risks. Joint work is also hindered by lacking employees with the knowledge and capacity to manage these projects. This project management task, they believe should be handled by higher education institutions.

Large companies can more easily meet reporting and regulatory obligations but face challenges. For example, a large company representative mentioned that despite their sustainability efforts, they can only achieve carbon neutrality by purchasing carbon credits. As previously mentioned, large companies have centrally defined guidelines related to circularity. While interviewees noted that they have a forward-looking sustainability strategy and that targets are set, the company's large size makes implementation slow and difficult.

The transition is further complicated because customer specifications often precede circular principles. One respondent shared an example where they wanted to use recycled plastic granulates to produce a part, but the customer required that the product contain no recycled material, as the regranulate weakened the mechanical properties. As a result, it was not feasible to incorporate recycled materials. The interviewee believes the possibility of applying circular principles depends on product requirements and sees limited potential for using recycled materials in the case of some plastics. Additionally, some production processes operate according to strictly laid down norms that the generation of by-products and waste cannot be further reduced.

In discussing the previous interview question, companies highlighted the value stored in materials as the primary solution, but it has many challenges. For instance, the emergence of new materials supporting the circular model requires new material processing, recycling, and extraction methods. The recycling of solar panels also poses a future challenge. If the focus shifts to the use of waste, solutions must be found for recycling and extracting an increasing variety of materials from waste, while waste processing capacity must also be expanded. However, declining production and consumption due to the economic recession worldwide reduce the amount of recyclable waste, affecting waste processing companies.

Reintroducing materials from complex products into the cycle is difficult because of their complexity. It is costly and time-consuming to separate them into reusable materials. It would be easier if disassembly was considered during the design phase, but this has not been addressed by the companies interviewed. Suppliers believe recyclability should be the responsibility of their partners who produce the final product.

Everyone agreed that the use of economically viable recyclable waste should be supported through appropriate incentives, subsidies, and EU decisions to avoid landfilling. Several participants emphasized the importance of selective collection in implementing the circular system. One of them noted that although the household's participation in the collection is increasing, further attitude changes are needed, which require improved communication. The new beverage packaging deposit-refund system introduced this year demonstrated that a high redemption rate can be achieved with the implementation of a deposit system. The interviewee believes that, based on this example, similar return systems have great potential, the right information (waste represents value) and monetary incentives are the best ways to motivate people in Hungary to recycle. However, many interview participants are wondering whether the overload and initial problems of REpontos will disappear over time, and whether it will be possible to create an efficiently functioning model.

Some respondents noted a minimal positive shift among manufacturers towards facilitating recycling, and the companies are trying to make some effort to consider circular principles. Many pointed out that, in addition to the participation of households, selective waste collection by industrial companies is essential to the circular economy because this makes collection and sorting easier for waste processors, and the manufacturer has a better overview of what kind and how much waste leaves the plant.

The selective collection and recycling of aluminium serve as a model for this. Industrial waste producers and demolition plants have been forced by wholesalers to sort aluminium according to alloys, creating a well-functioning market for economically viable aluminium

recycling. Thanks to this, aluminium waste is available in an economically recyclable quantity in Hungary, and with proper preparation, a high proportion of recycling is achieved.

However, for other materials, the amount of waste is too small to make it possible to build a profitable recycling infrastructure, so most materials are exported and recycled in the European market rather than in Hungary. This is due to the small size of the country and the inefficient collection. One potential solution for materials that cannot be economically processed locally is to use them as fuel in power plants, though not all materials are suitable or easily usable for burning. One interviewee cited PVC as an example, as burning it releases harmful substances. He suggested using recycled PVC granulates in door and window production to avoid landfilling.

The respondents emphasized the importance of focusing on materials that are easier to treat or directly reintegrate into production processes. Achieving this requires current processing systems to produce pure materials that can serve as high-quality secondary raw materials.

More participants mentioned that to reach the climate and digital objectives of the European Union, the European industry has an extremely high demand for critical raw materials. Through legislation, the EU wants to ensure that European industry has access to critical raw materials safely and sustainably and is less dependent on countries that are the only suppliers of a particular material. This problem highlights the need to develop technologies for recovering these materials from waste.

Although interviewees think Hungary is making good progress in meeting the EU's waste-related targets, several expressed disagreements about the centralization of waste management. They argued that the market should determine the economy and not be distorted by centralization. They believe the system is unnecessary and is not working efficiently, requiring further development and more competent professionals. Previously, there were well-functioning waste collection and sorting systems, but centralization has resulted in increased costs, complicated collection, inadequate preparation, and economically unviable waste recycling. The participants believe current practices must change, and incentives should be provided to promote the production of high-quality secondary raw materials. A representative of one manufacturing company noted that since the centralization of waste management, meeting their recycling goals has become more difficult due to the introduction of new waste categories. Despite these challenges, the respondents remain optimistic and can already see improvements in the system.

4.2.4. *The role of universities in the transition to CE*

Several interviewees believe that the academic world's lobbying power could play a significant role in developing and implementing new circular business models. In their opinion, higher education institutions should influence the European Union and national regulations related to circular technologies.

Some emphasized that capitalizing on the opportunities of the circular economy could be key to regional development in the future. For instance, creating CE technology-related competence centres could support the transition and regional growth.

Most of the companies consider university partnerships especially important. One participant stated that the emergence of a circular approach requires new types of knowledge and specialists who are currently unavailable in the labour market. Another interview highlighted that the market lacks the expertise to develop optimal energy use for a facility. According to the respondents, universities are responsible for developing and launching educational programmes tailored to these new needs. Enterprises can contribute to the new CE technology-related courses by offering practical experience, such as internships, jointly developed educational programmes, and dual training courses. Businesses expressed a desire to support the education of future professionals but noted that fewer students come to them each year, and the students have only theoretical knowledge, lacking practical training. Companies want more practical education; to achieve this, they need closer partnerships with universities.

Another avenue of cooperation with higher education institutions is using and sharing technical knowledge, professional resources, and university infrastructure. However, several participants mentioned obstacles: although they have connections with certain institutes, they have only limited awareness of available resources, labs, and institutes, making it challenging to identify potential collaboration points. Getting to know the service portfolio would be important for them, to address this, one participant suggested organizing company-university open days, combined with laboratory visits.

Most interviewees emphasized the importance of events connecting representatives from industry and academia. In addition to learning about university services, they would attend such events to gather information. With the rapid advancement of science, new research and discoveries constantly emerge, but most businesses lack the capacity to keep up with or deeply understand them. According to the firms, universities should gather, organize, and filter relevant information and present it to industry representatives. Universities, with their

instrumental and knowledge base, could help bring new technologies to a level suitable for industrial use, for example, by establishing pilot plants and equipment.

Most research participants think there is huge potential in circular technologies, but many topics remain unresearched by Hungarian higher education institutions.

Companies expressed the intention of research collaborations, but various obstacles have emerged connected to the joint work. On the one hand, enterprises struggle to keep up with institutional changes (e.g., faculty reorganizations, renaming), making it difficult to know whom to contact and what research opportunities are available. On the other hand, even though past initiatives for cooperation have been made, there was often no specific, defined task to start real collaboration. To solve this, one participant suggested that after establishing contact with the company, the university should form a team of experts to work together on finding solutions, including searching for call for proposals.

Some businesses noted that, in previous collaborations, higher education institutions had the theoretical background but lacked the necessary equipment for practical implementation. They found that joint projects imposed a large administrative burden, and sometimes, the research did not yield usable results.

Despite these challenges, several companies wanted to implement joint research projects related to circular technologies. Grouped according to the circular cycle, potential future collaborations could focus on the following areas:

Manufacturing:

- Packaging material design
- Use of green energy in metallurgical processes
- Utilization of oxygen produced during water electrolysis
- Energy use modernization
- Modernization of CO₂ recovery methods

Logistics:

- Coordination of production waste and by-product material flows

Repair, refurbishment, and remanufacturing:

- Efficiency-enhancing methods for fault detection
- Automation and the use of artificial intelligence

Recycling:

- Development of technologies and models for recycling and processing materials not yet (or currently only in a small proportion) recycled

- Investigation of recycling possibilities for new raw materials and waste types

Waste Management:

- Utilization of aluminum oxide salt remaining from aluminum slag
- Treatment of residual sewage sludge
- Management, sorting, and processing of production waste

Sustainable energy (production):

- Simulations and process modeling
- Recycling of spent fuel
- Utilization of surplus solar power production
- Production of green hydrogen
- Use of geothermal energy to meet plant energy needs

It is important to note that joint research and projects are mainly feasible with SMEs. In the case of large companies, cooperation is usually hindered by a top-down approach to technological development, where they must adhere to centrally defined norms and strategies. These companies cannot influence global operations, but they can provide insight into their successful practices, for example, through workshops, which could benefit SMEs.

4.3. Evaluation of the results: answering research questions

Despite the questionnaire reached a large target audience, compared to this, only few responses were received. This is likely because most companies are not interested in circular technologies until they are forced by legislation to operate more sustainably.

While the questionnaire sample cannot be considered representative, its representativeness is improved by the fact that 64% of the respondents were from the SME sector. This reflects the proportions of industrial companies in Hungary if micro-enterprises are excluded. (99% of enterprises are SMEs, but almost 94% are micro-enterprises, of which only a tiny portion engage in industrial activities.) This ratio by size was also roughly reflected in the interviewees. The majority of companies that completed the questionnaire operate in industrial subsectors where production value is the highest, placing them among the most significant. The enterprises interviewed cover almost the entire circular economy regarding their activities. Furthermore, since most of them operate in the Northern Hungary region, it can be stated that their responses provide a solid basis for developing suggestions to support this region's growth.

Summarizing the results from the questionnaire and in-depth interviews, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Q1: What knowledge do companies have about the circular economy?

The companies are familiar with the definition of the circular economy, and most of them have at least some knowledge of the related guidelines and regulations. They are already involved in or want to engage in professional activities on this topic. Therefore, they possess basic knowledge of the circular approach and are likely open to deepening their understanding, building a professional community, and making improvements and investments in circular technologies.

Q2: What does the absorption of CE technologies mean for companies, and how do they apply circularity in their operation?

Many enterprises are already applying the aspects of the circular economy to some extent, particularly in energy consumption, materials, and waste. In the future, their focus will also be primarily on these areas. Besides these, they aspire to more significant progress in logistics activities and requirements towards their suppliers. Circular product design, activities related to tracking and extending product lifespan, and consumer attitudes shaping programs are still unexploited development areas because, currently, few companies are engaged in these topics or plan to deal with them. When companies think of the circular economy, they focus on efficient material and energy use. It is important to reinforce that the circular model encompasses more than this; it requires a holistic approach covering the entire lifecycle—from raw materials, manufacturing, and product use, to post-use activities. The adoption of circular technologies is mostly influenced by external factors, such as legislative pressure, the possible advantages gained in tender/grant evaluations, and the marketing value of sustainable operation.

Q3: What are the barriers to the absorption of CE technologies?

Currently, the legal and economic environment is the most significant inhibiting factor, which does not adequately support the transition to the circular model. Although the area of the circular economy has appeared in the call for proposals and grant systems, support is primarily given for investment and development. Applying circular technologies is not yet viewed as advantageous for companies in terms of operational costs. Economic incentives are needed to encourage the use of secondary raw materials over primary ones (e.g., lower VAT rate for secondary raw materials).

The factors hindering the absorption of circular technologies in Hungarian industrial companies can be summarized as follows:

Legal and regulatory environment: Regulations are too complex and change rapidly, making compliance difficult. Too many documentation and administration tasks and a shortage of specialists to meet the regulations. There is also a lack of comprehensive regulations covering the entire circular economy; instead, there are too many sub-area regulations.

Economic environment: Economic policy decisions are made without sufficient industry involvement and analysis their possible effects. Rapidly changing economic environment, laws, and economic downturn present challenges.

Profit maximization: Customer requirements and economic considerations (maximizing profit and minimizing costs) take priority over sustainability.

Declining investment and R&D willingness: The unpredictable economic environment and quickly changing regulations discourage investment. Bureaucratic processes, delayed payments, unclear responsibilities and tasks, and a lack of knowledge and resources for R+D project management hinder joint projects with universities.

Challenges related to materials and waste: Limited possibilities for incorporating recycled materials. There is a need to develop new extraction and preparation methods and technologies (e.g., separation of multi-component materials and solutions for processing new types of materials and waste). Inefficient selective waste collection, and the initial challenges of the centralized waste management system. A lack of return systems covers a wide range of waste types. The problem is that waste cannot be economically recycled locally. The need to shape consumer attitudes. Europe's dependence on other countries for critical raw materials is also a significant issue.

Lack of product lifetime extension efforts: Regulations are not strict enough, there is a need for new business models, and circular principles are not widely applied in product design.

Lack of information: There is currently no wholesale marketplace or platform for the sale of secondary raw materials, by-products, and defective semi-finished or final products. This lack of infrastructure hinders collaborations based on industrial symbiosis. Efficient information flow between companies is needed, along with well-organized logistics systems to optimize the use of secondary raw materials and production capacity (e.g., smaller repair and refurbishment plants supplementing larger companies' missing repair capacities).

Q4: What role can the University of Miskolc play in eliminating the barriers to the absorption of CE technologies?

Most companies believe universities can play a critical role in the transition to a circular economy. Nearly three-quarters of the interviewees expressed interest in using university services, indicating a demand for them. The University of Miskolc can help eliminate barriers to technology absorption through the following activities:

Influencing regulation: Supporting the creation of an appropriate legal and economic environment for the circular economy through lobbying and counselling.

Establishing competence centres: Exploiting the circular economy's potential by establishing competence centres related to circular technology, which can drive regional development and growth.

Teaching new knowledge related to circular technologies: Developing educational materials, launching new programmes in close cooperation with industry (implementing practice-oriented education that meets market needs).

Providing services for companies tailored to demand: Offering innovation, waste management, R+D project funding, and technology consultation services. Searching for problems that arise at companies, setting up a group of experts to solve the problem after contact, and full follow-up of the work.

Sharing technical knowledge, resources, and infrastructure: Developing circular technologies to an industry-usable level, offering laboratory services, and conducting joint research.

Implementing R+D projects with companies: Monitoring grant opportunities related to circular technologies, seeking corporate partners, preparing projects to reduce company risks (clarification of tasks and responsibilities), and providing university project managers for implementation.

Knowledge sharing: Summarizing and filtering new research results on circular technologies, presenting them to companies, and sharing best practices (e.g., through workshops). Helping in the coordination of secondary raw material flows.

Several companies have already cooperated with the University of Miskolc in the field of the CE technology, and many are open to starting joint research and development projects. The University of Miskolc has competence and references in this area, presenting a significant opportunity to effectively support companies in Northern Hungary to improve their technology absorption and innovation capacity. In the future, the planned CiRCLETECH Hub can provide

valuable services to the university's industrial partners in the areas explored in this study, facilitating the transfer of research results to industry, the transition to a circular economy, and the industrial collaboration systems. Thanks to these steps, a more sustainable future can be achieved, and the economic growth and development of the region can also increase.

5. Presentation of the identified good practices

5.1. Good practices at the examined companies

Borsodi Sörgyár Kft.

Their sustainability strategy, called *Our Imprint*, envisions leaving a positive legacy for future generations. To achieve this, they are taking action on water, climate change, and packaging. They strive to use the energy efficiently and reduce losses (e.g., by installing proper insulation), and they also try to cover their energy demand with energy from renewable sources. Their own biogas plant partially provides the site's energy supply, and they have installed a 500kW solar panel park on the roof. Carbon dioxide from the beer fermentation process is recovered, purified through a regenerator, and reused in their operational processes. Their main by-product, malt pomace, is sold for animal feed, ensuring it is also utilized and does not become waste. The company's products are packaged in recyclable aluminum and reusable glass packaging, and the site's recyclable waste is sold through MOHU partners.

Metal Shredder Hungary Zrt.

Metal Shredder Hungary Zrt. plays a significant role in ensuring that EU directives and targets are met in Hungary regarding the materials they process. They carry out R&D activities and operate according to the circular approach. The company specializes in the recycling of electronic waste, mainly dealing with the extraction of precious metals, but they also process discarded X-ray films. They have a well-established collection network and logistics, for example, they handle equipment scrapped during electronic device renewal programmes of institutions. The waste is broken down into materials, aluminium is recycled through the firm's subcontractors. The extracted precious metals (gold, silver, palladium, platinum) are sold in block form, as finished products. The carrier metals of the precious metals are also sold in block form, the company has a partner who remelts the copper waste back into production, thus the circularity is realized.

PL3 Javító, Szolgáltató és Tanácsadó Kft.

The company's mission is to increase the lifespan of electronic devices, which is achieved through repair, refurbishment, remanufacturing, and preventive maintenance. Their main activity is to repair printed circuit boards after fault finding and diagnosis, then reassemble them into the device. On the one hand, they repair serially defective parts and finished products containing printed circuit boards from multinational companies in large volumes (e.g., the surface-mounting technology's error during manufacturing); on the other hand, defective devices within and outside the warranty are repaired in the plant. After the service, the devices are returned to their original area of use, but they can also be converted by adding new functions or making them suitable for other areas of use (e.g. remanufacturing traditional tablets for use in explosive environments).

ALU-BLOCK Kft.

The company produces casting alloy blocks from aluminium waste, which serves as a raw material for their aluminium casting manufacturer customers operating primarily in the automotive and construction industries. They receive the waste in bulk or in bales from their partners who selectively collect the metal, and the production waste directly from the foundries. The prepared material (baled in the case of bulk waste) is melted in a furnace, alloyed, and then casted into a mould to form a block. Their customers then produce foundry products from these blocks. It is important for the company to manage waste efficiently and sustainably, using the most modern equipment and production technology available, and they are constantly adapting to new materials and their recycling. Thanks to their activity, circularity is realized in a closed system. They think in terms of local circularity, they consider it important to process waste generated locally and to sell the finished products locally.

5.2. Good practices at LUT

One of the partner institutions of the CIRCLETECH project, Lappeenranta University of Technology (LUT), is very similar in size to the University of Miskolc, moreover, its main

research focus is sustainability, so the good practices of LUT can serve as a model for the University of Miskolc in terms of corporate and regional relations, research management and services. The LUT has also achieved exemplary results (e.g. international university rankings) in the fields of green transition, climate protection and circular economy in research and cooperation with companies. The research management practice at LUT could be a good basis for the University of Miskolc. The focused research directions of the institution are as follows:

- Air purity protection
- Water purity, treatment
- Energetics - achieving carbon neutrality
- Sustainable business solutions and society

The LUT focuses all its entire training and research on these directions, which are built around a common set of principles.

Table 2 LUT and University of Miskolc in numbers

	LUT	University of Miskolc
Number of students (persons)	7.000	11.000
Number of employees (persons)	1.200	1.300
QS International Ranking	351	1.200 - 1.400
THE international ranking	251-300	738
EUList membership	yes	not
University Climate Action Plan	yes	not

Table 2 compares the University of Miskolc with the University of LUT in numbers. Based on these:

- The number of students at the two universities is similar
- The number of employees at the two universities is similar
- Due to the LUT's well-focused operations it ranks higher in international rankings compared to the University of Miskolc.
- The Finnish university is also a member of the internationally recognised European University Association EULIST.

- In 2020, LUT adopted its Climate Action Plan (2021-2024), as a result of which the operation of the institution became climate neutral by 2024

LUT's success is partly due to the organisational structure within the university, which has been named the Research Group. Research Groups have been set up for priority research areas, where all horizontal research activities are integrated.

Another reason for LUT's success is its well-organised, transparent structure, as the university's website shows. The main topics are clearly separated, the website is easy to navigate and you can see what the LUT is all about:

- study opportunities (different courses),
- what research is being done (projects, research teams, infrastructure),
- the opportunities for cooperation between companies (joint research, investment opportunities, start-up companies).

A forward-looking activity is the support of start-up and spinoff companies at LUT, mainly thanks to successful participation in programmes announced by Business Finland (a public venture capital fund). Every year, 3-4 start-up companies win project grants of €1.5-2 million, involving students and academics.

The university's cooperation with the city of Lappeenranta and the region is exemplary. The city and the region generate joint projects with the LUT and participate jointly in Finnish and international projects. Some of the joint projects in which LUT and the city are currently involved:

- UIR - Urban Infra Revolution (<https://www.uia-initiative.eu/en/uia-cities/lappeenranta>)
- 5R Refinery - Sewage sludge recovery
- ThreadingCO2 (Horizon Europe project) - carbon sequestration in polyester fibres
- Resident-oriented Circular Economy solutions for the citizens in South Karelia - ASKI
- Exploitation of mining waste
- Lappeenranta Junior University programme for young people.

Summary

A survey about Hungarian circular economy was previously conducted only by the Circular Economy Platform. This study differs from that research, because it also includes in-depth personal interviews, which provide more grounded conclusions. Additionally, it prioritizes the industrial companies from the SMEs sector and the Northern Hungary region, and describes the role of innovation and technology absorption in regional growth.

Based on the survey, the following can be summarized:

- The concept and importance of the circular economy have become known to companies.
- Most businesses have not yet fully implemented the circular model.
- Related to CE technology, most companies focus primarily on managing the waste generated during production and reducing energy consumption.
- Several companies have also started taking advantage of marketing opportunities by showcasing their commitment to achieving a circular economy on their websites and in promotional materials.
- Most companies do not yet focus on monitoring the product lifetime, customer awareness shaping programmes, and developing product design according to circular principles.
- Hungarian companies agree that the introduction of a full-scale circular model would represent a significant financial burden. As a result, they expect a more defined legislative environment from the government, including specific obligations for individual economic actors, and propose the introduction of economic incentives to help implement circular technologies.
- Companies primarily see the role of universities in knowledge sharing for the development of the circular model. While they would like to use an innovation service, SMEs cannot finance R+D projects independently. Large companies, especially foreign-owned multinational corporations, typically have the resources for development, but they also seek grants for university collaborations.

During the in-depth interviews, it became clear that many companies are interested in collaborating with universities, particularly the University of Miskolc. Several topics were identified that could serve as starting points for joint work in this area. With its existing competencies and laboratory infrastructure, the University of Miskolc can play a central role in the development of the circular economy in Northern Hungary, and even on a national level.

Based on international examples and trends, it is expected that the circular economy model will fundamentally change not only the world but also our immediate environment. In the Northern Hungary region, it is important to be not only followers of this trend but also pioneers, both in Hungary and Europe. As a knowledge centre, the University of Miskolc plays a key role in regional innovation, the training of future generations, and has a social responsibility, in line with its third mission, for the development of the region.

The study's results shows that there are already good corporate examples that can help achieve these goals. The University of Miskolc's competencies are well-suited for providing technical, economic, and legal support for the circular economic model. However, to make effective progress, it is important to give this area greater prominence within the university (as the circular economy keyword does not currently appear among its listed competencies).

A strong university-company collaboration system has already been established in the area of corporate research management. However, it would be beneficial to introduce new organizational forms in terms of competence (such as horizontal research platforms that cross faculties) to enhance information flow and knowledge transfer, like the model of research groups at LUT.

The University of Miskolc has applied for the Science Park call for proposal by the Hungarian government. This project's primary mission is to create a university-based innovation ecosystem and foster research, development, and innovation activities in cooperation with innovative companies in the Northern Hungary region. The Science Park aims to continuously encourage regional RDI activities, corporate collaborations, and the development and operation of technology-intensive enterprises, including spin-offs.

This process can be further supported by the university's innovation ecosystem, where 100% university-owned enterprises operate under the so-called TTC (Technology Transfer Company) model, already established at most Hungarian universities. The TTC model aims to accelerate the commercialization of university knowledge, bring intellectual products to market, and create new spin-off businesses. The University of Miskolc also plans to implement this model, which is expected to effectively help the creation of a circular ecosystem in the region.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Questionnaire

CiRCLETECH questionnaire

Survey on the application of technology solutions related to the circular economy

As part of the CiRCLETECH international project, the University of Miskolc is conducting research on the relationship and experiences of Hungarian industrial companies with the circular economy (CE). The aim of the research is to identify the barriers to the absorption of CE technologies. By improving technological absorption, the innovation capacity can be increased, which is the cornerstone of competitiveness today. Circular solutions are expected to become a European Union directive, so discussing this topic may be important for your company as well.

Please assist our work by completing the questionnaire, which takes less than 10 minutes. We will provide a summary of the results on the project website (<https://circletech-hub.eu/>), which will be available in October 2024.

Before filling out the questionnaire, you can learn more about the circular economy here: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/en/article/20151201STO05603/circular-economy-definition-importance-and-benefits>

General information

1. In which industrial sub-section does your company operate? If there is more than one, please indicate the industry related to your main field of activity!

- Manufacture of coke, and refined petroleum products
- Pharmaceutical industry
- Chemical industry
- Manufacture of transport equipment
- Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products
- Manufacture of machinery
- Rubber and plastic industry
- Furniture and wood industry
- Manufacture of electrical equipment
- Manufacture of basic metals and fabricated metal products

- Food industry
- Textile industry
- Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply
- Mining and quarrying
- Other: _____

2. Which category does your company belong to by business size?

- Small enterprise (max. 49 employees)
- Medium-sized enterprise (max. 249 employees)
- Large enterprise (250 or more employees)

3. In which region does your company operate? (More than one answer is possible.)

- Central Hungary
- Northern Hungary
- Northern Great Plain
- Southern Great Plain
- Central Transdanubia
- Western Transdanubia
- Southern Transdanubia

The definition of the circular economy

4. Have you ever heard of the concept of the circular economy?

- Yes, I know the concept of the circular economy.
- Yes, I have heard of it, but I do not know it in detail.
- No.

5. What is the definition of the circular economy?

- A model that focuses exclusively on the efficient utilization of waste.
- A model that focuses exclusively on environmentally friendly solutions of the energy management.

- A system-based model that focuses on prolonging the product lifetime as much as possible instead of one-time consumption, and the efficient utilization of resources in them (materials, energy).
- A model that focuses exclusively on reducing carbon dioxide emissions and climate protection.

6. At the EU level, the *Circular Economy Action Plan*, in Hungary the *Climate and Environmental Protection Action Plan*, the *National Waste Management Plan 2021-2027*, and the *Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) system* serve as a framework for the circular economy. Have you ever heard of them, or do you know their content?

	I have heard about it	I know its content	I have not heard of it and do not know its content
Circular Economy Action Plan			
Climate and Environmental Protection Action Plan			
National Waste Management Plan 2021-2027			
Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) system			

Circular operation at your company

7. Does your company take the aspects of the circular economy into account during its activities?

- Yes, completely.
- Yes, partly.
- No, but we plan to consider it in the future.
- No, and we do not plan to use it.

8. In which areas does your company apply the aspects of the circular economy? (Multiple answers are possible)

- Product design
- Raw material procurement

- Requirements for our suppliers
- Manufacturing technology
- Energy consumption
- Management of production waste
- Logistics activities
- Monitoring the life cycle of the product (product exchange, servicing etc.)
- Business model
- Consumer attitudes shaping programmes
- We do not apply it in any area
- Other: _____

9. In which areas do you plan to advance in your company in order to develop a circular model? (Multiple answers are possible)

- Product design
- Raw material procurement
- Requirements for our suppliers
- Manufacturing technology
- Energy consumption
- Management of production waste
- Logistics activities
- Monitoring the life cycle of the product (product exchange, servicing etc.)
- Business model
- Consumer attitudes shaping programmes
- We do not plan to advance in any area
- Other: _____

10. Please evaluate on a scale from 1 to 5 how much impact the following factors have on the adoption of circular technological solutions in your company:

(1 - No effect at all, 2 - Rather no effect, 3 - Moderate effect, 4 - Rather has an effect, 5 - Very large effect)

	1	2	3	4	5
Regulatory/legal pressure					
Pressure from other companies to whom we are suppliers					
Change in employee attitudes/employee demands					
The possibility of increasing competitiveness					
The possibility of gaining an advantage in the evaluation of tenders/grants					
Improving the image of the company in consumers/partners					
Owner/management demand for greener operation					

11. Please evaluate on a scale from 1 to 5 the extent of the following factors may hinder the adoption of circular technological solutions in your company:

(1 – Does not prevent at all, 2 - Rather does not prevent, 3 - Moderately prevents, 4 - Rather prevents, 5 - Strongly prevents)

	1	2	3	4	5
Financial constraints					
Lack of expertise					
Bureaucratic regulation					
Other economic factors are more important in the industry					
Absence of central programmes and guidance					
Attitude of employees					
Lack of relational capital and information					

12. In your opinion, (apart from those listed in the previous question) are there any other factors that can prevent the implementation of circular aspects in your company? If so, please enter them in the "Other" field!

Other: _____

13. Is your company currently a member of any professional community, or has it recently participated in a conference or event related to the circular economy?

	Yes	No, but I plan to	No, and I do not plan to
Membership in a professional community			
Conference/event participation			

Assessment of demand for CE services

14. In which areas would your company require external services (consulting) for the development of the circular operation model? (Multiple answers are possible)

- Innovation services (product/technology/social/business innovation, tech transfer, industrial property)
- Business
- Technology
- Energy management
- Waste management
- Tenders, grants, funding opportunities
- I would not require any services
- Other: _____

15. Would your company use university services in connection with circular operations?

- Yes
- No

Closing

By clicking on Send button, you complete the questionnaire and your answers are saved.

By clicking on Send button, I declare that I have read and understood the *Privacy Policy* for the questionnaire. The *Data protection and data processing guide* of the University of Miskolc is available on the following website: <https://www.uni-miskolc.hu/egyetemunk/kozerdeku-adatok/adatkezeles/>.

16. Would you like to participate in a 30-minute interview to discuss your company's good practices related to the circular economy with experts from the University of Miskolc?

- Yes, in person
- Yes, online
- No

17. If you answered 'Yes' to the previous question, please enter your email address so we can contact you!

.....

Appendix 2: Interview questions

1. In the questionnaire, you responded to the question, "*In which areas does your company apply the aspects of the circular economy?*" by marking the following areas:

...

Could you provide specific examples, practices, technologies, etc., related to these areas? Do you have any specific criteria for your suppliers related to the circular economy? If so, what are they?

2. In the questionnaire, you responded to the question, "*In which areas do you plan to advance in your company in order to develop a circular model?*" by marking the following areas: ...

Could you provide specific examples, practices, technologies, etc., related to these areas? Do you plan to apply any requirements for your suppliers related to the circular economy? If so, what are they?

3. What negative attitudes characterize your company regarding the transition to circular operation? What are the company's fears, and what risks do you anticipate regarding the change (e.g., circular technologies may lead to an increase in costs)? What actions are being taken to mitigate these risks? What weaknesses (internal factors preventing the achievement of the goal) and threats (external factors preventing the achievement of the goal) are present in your company related to the implementation of circular solutions?

4. Secondary raw material streams play an important role in the circular model. Has your company already been involved in a secondary value stream and/or implemented recovery from your own production waste? If so, in what form?

What kind of help does your company need to achieve this? What value network could you envision for your company (possible receivers of your waste and your potential secondary raw material suppliers)?

5. What role do you expect higher education institutions and academic circles to play in the transition to circular operation at your company? Is it only an organizational and attitude-shaping role (e.g., organization of conferences, workshops, communities), or do you foresee a closer, more practical cooperation (e.g., development of a circular strategy for your company, utilization of research results in your company, joint research, submission of tenders as a consortium)?